

A Study on “BURDEN ASSESSMENT OF THE WIVES OF ALCOHOLICS” With special reference to - Hyderabad, Telangana state

Dr. M. Vijay Kumar Sharma

Dept of Social Work, Telangana University,
QSouth campus, Biknoor, Kamareddy, Nizamabad
Telangana State-503102

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6674112>

Published Date: 21-June-2022

Abstract: Alcohol promotes the accumulation of fat in the liver, a disease known as "fatty infiltration of the liver." Large numbers of liver cells die in some alcoholics, causing the liver to become inflamed, enlarged, and painful, a disease known as "alcoholic hepatitis." When a large number of cells are killed, scar tissue forms, resulting in "cirrhosis" of the liver. Alcoholism is a condition that affects not only the individual but also his entire family. The loss of a job will devastate the family's financial situation. A role model reversal occurs when the breadwinner becomes an alcoholic and the wife assumes the position of earning — marital discord is a regular issue. Alcoholism is a sickness that affects the entire family, particularly the spouses. Wives of alcoholics suffer a slew of issues and stress. The children of an alcoholic home are unable to focus on their education. Because of her stress and anxiety, some spouses are unable to properly care for their children. According to research, many alcoholics' wives committed suicide as a result of home problems as well as social isolation. The present study was conducted to assess the burden on wives of alcoholics with 80 respondents in Hyderabad. It was found that majority of alcoholic's wives are very pathetic; they are begrimed woman retaining her possession. The major problem is she has anxiety about the future of her children. The role of father and mother are combined here. The mother, she is struggling hard to keep the family in the traumatic situation she has faced due to this alcoholism which has physical, mental and emotional implication.

Keywords: Alcoholism, Stress, Marital discord, Anxiety.

1. INTRODUCTION

Alcoholism is a complex social problem that affects not only the person who is familiar with it, but also all of his family members and the processes of a social structure. It is linked to a wide range of causes. It causes the total breakdown of family ties, particularly marital ones, as well as all types of relationships. Over the last few years, it has been increasingly evident to the entire globe that alcoholism has evolved into a major social problem encompassing not only individual and family maladaptive behavior, but also bigger groupings, including entire societies.

Alcoholism is one of the most serious societal issues that modern men face. It impacts practically everyone, regardless of their socioeconomic status. Consumption of alcoholic beverages is harmful to one's health. It causes a slew of illnesses. A whole health problem for the alcoholic, in addition to the fact that alcoholics cause several problems in society and in their own homes. The children of an alcoholic home are unable to focus on their education. Because of her stress and

anxiety, some spouses are unable to properly care for their children. According to research, many alcoholics' wives committed suicide as a result of home problems as well as social isolation.

IMPACT OF ALCOHOLISM AS A DISEASE

Alcoholism is a condition that affects not only the individual but also his entire family. The loss of a job will devastate the family's financial situation. A role model reversal occurs when the breadwinner becomes an alcoholic and the wife assumes the position of earning — marital discord is a regular issue. Alcoholism is a sickness that affects the entire family, particularly the spouses. Wives of alcoholics suffer a slew of issues and stress. Alcoholism is described as a condition in which a person loses control over his alcohol consumption and is unable to stop once he starts. According to Keller and Efron, alcoholism is defined as excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages or complaints about community social traditions that interfere with the drinker's health, social, or economic functioning.

Until a few decades ago, alcoholism was regarded as a moral issue and a symptom of social irresponsibility, but today's experts regard it as a complex chronic and extremely costly disease rather than a form of deviant behaviour. Alcoholism was classified as a disease by the American Medical Association, the World Health Organization, and many other professional organisations. Alcoholism is a significant condition that affects not only the drinker but also the people around him or her. It has a direct impact on his wife. It produces an unfavourable household environment. Others are connected with every man who drinks. One of the most serious issues with drinking is that it turns a person into a personal and social problem. When under the influence of alcohol, the heavy drinker may be talkative or gloomily silent for the sake of his house, family, and business. To the sober listener, his discourse may appear coarse. As a result, all of this has an impact on the wives.¹⁰

The importance of familiar intervention with alcoholics cannot be stressed for a variety of reasons. Family issues like marital strife and financial strains can add to the rising stress levels that lead to binge drinking. It also has a negative impact on the family's social, economic, and emotional well-being. Several home remedies, such as emptying the liquor bottle, looking them up with money, and so on, have been tried. At first, married couples discuss the issue calmly and pleasantly, but eventually become enraged and blame each other. He employs a range of emotional arguments to get him to stop drinking. Due to a multitude of factors, including increased availability, increased life stresses, and the collapse of traditional values and family life, substance addiction problems have been on the rise in recent years. Substance abuse has serious consequences for a person's family and community. It has a negative impact on the health, psychological well-being, family life, social status, working capacity, and academic development of young people. Alcoholism is a problem that affects many people. Mental or physical illness, as well as a family history, can have an impact on a person's life.

ALCOHOLISM AND THEIR FAMILY Alcoholism affects the entire family

Living in a household with a non-recovering alcoholic can be stressful for everyone. Each person may be affected in a unique way. Not every alcoholic family can cope with stress in the same way. Children who are raised in alcoholic homes have different life experiences than children who are raised in non-alcoholic homes. Children raised in various types of dysfunctional households, as well as children raised in alcoholic families, may endure developmental losses and stressors that are similar. Children who live with a non-recovering alcoholic score lower on measures of family cohesion, intellectual-cultural orientation, and independence. Furthermore, they are more likely to experience family conflict. Many alcoholics' offspring view other family members as distant and uncommunicative (COAs). The inability of alcoholics' children to develop in a developmentally healthy manner may be a barrier to their development. The level of dysfunction or resiliency of the non-alcoholic spouse is a crucial factor in the children's reactions to issues.

EFFECTS OF ALCOHOLISMS ON THE INDIVIDUALS, FAMILY AND SOCIETY.

The individual can be affected by heart failure, liver disease, cancer, pancreatitis, malnutrition and of course, psychological and emotional problems. The high levels of alcohol and acetaldehyde after the shape and functioning of the heart muscle. Enzymes leak from the cells, the cell are damaged, and eventually fat infiltrated them, causing mechanisms that regulate the heart can be affected and death can be caused by heart failure. Alcohol also contributes to the buildup of fat in the liver, leading to a condition known as “fatty infiltration of the liver”. In some alcoholics, large numbers of liver cells die and the liver becomes inflamed, swollen and tender, a condition called “alcoholic hepatitis”. When so many cells are destroyed that scar tissue begins to form “Cirrhosis” of the liver results. If alcohol affects the lining of the stomach, gastrointestinal problems result; Alcoholics can also become susceptible to reparatory tract diseases

when alcohol interferes with the body's normal immune systems. Large doses of alcohol can also injure the pancreas, causing it to release digestive enzymes, which aggravate the inflammation of the pancreas. There are also indications that large amount of alcohol may aggravate cancer in the body.

EFFECTS OF ALCOHOLISM ON WIVES:

An alcoholic has a direct impact on the lives of family members, friends, and employees. However, it is the family that is most at risk. Robinson, Rod. Alcoholics typically neglect their family in order to focus on their drinking, and they vent their frustrations on their loved ones through verbal, emotional, or physical abuse. They also neglect their commitments to their families, causing their husbands and children to shoulder some of their tasks. This can rise to feelings of isolation, loneliness, insecurity, and wrath, and an alcoholic spouse is frequently aggressive to his wife. It's difficult to envisage a non-abusive alcoholic husband. He is generally verbally abusive and demeaning her dignity or emotionally withdrawn if he does not punch her, toss items, or ruin the furniture.

This will eventually wear her down to the point where she may not have the self-esteem to break out. As a result, she may find herself on a rough path. She could have encountered damaged pride, frustration, self-pity, misunderstanding, and dread. An alcoholic's long-term partner is unlikely to have a regular lifestyle that promotes to a long and healthy life. She's probably dealing with the problem to the point where she doesn't eat regularly, exercise regularly, or sleep in a healthy manner. She is always concerned about her difficulties, and thoughts about her and her children's future may arise at any time. Stress levels are high, and depression is frequent. Women say they are exhausted. Typically, they will have to work outside the home to support the family and then take care of all of the other responsibilities that a husband and wife should share.

Rehabilitation

Following the cessation of drinking, the next stage is to assist the patient in avoiding ever drinking again. Rehabilitation is the term for this stage of treatment. The greatest programmes include the patient's family in therapy because the patient's drinking has surely had a negative impact on the family. Some therapists feel that in an effort to help their loved ones deal with their drinking problems, family members might establish patterns of conduct that unintentionally promote or "enable" the patient's drinking. This is known as "co-dependency," and it must be addressed in order to successfully treat an individual's alcoholism. There are also drugs that can assist an alcoholic in avoiding relapse. These have had varying degrees of success. When used with alcohol, disulfiram (Antabuse) induces a highly unpleasant reaction that includes nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, and shaking. Acamprosate and naltrexone have been shown to help reduce the impact of a relapse. None of these drugs would be effective unless the patient was also ready to put in a lot of effort to change his or her habits.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jones A. Jackson (1954) did research on the stress levels of alcoholics' wives. The behaviour of alcoholic women as a crisis reaction triggered by the stress caused by the presence of an alcoholic in the home. Denial of the problem, attempts to eradicate the problem, disorganisation, attempts to recognise despite the problem, endeavour to flee from the problems, recognition of a family member, recovery, and reorganisation are the seven stages of family adjustment to alcoholism.

A research on the relationship between an alcoholic and his wife was undertaken by Lewin (1957). He tells how difficult it was for an alcoholic and his wife to have a relationship. Such a woman found an outlet for her angry tendencies in her relationship with a man who was very reliant on her and who forced her to punish him. Both partners took turns playing "masculine" and "feminine" roles.

Domestic violence, stress, and coping among alcoholic spouses were studied by M. Sreedevi, Gangadhariah, and V. Benegal (2000). The most common problem in the family as a result of alcoholism is violence, which includes physical abuse on the wife, assault on children, and property destruction. The goal of the study was to look into the problem of domestic violence encountered by wives of alcoholics, as well as the stress that comes with it and the coping styles that these women use to deal with it. Domestic violence was a prevalent occurrence in the study.

Sobhaney (1974) investigated the family and social backgrounds of alcoholics. The sample included 30 households of non-alcohol dependent people and 30 families of alcoholics. The normal was primarily investigated in the context of

family contact. The author came to the conclusion that alcoholic families had greater resentment, hostility, disputes, and verbal or physical conflicts. There was also evidence of both hidden and overt kinds of animosity.

NS Cotton (1988) The marriage of an alcoholic is sometimes perceived as a fight for power. The non-alcoholic spouse may appear overly responsible and domineering, as well as taking on an overly functional role. In contrast to alcoholics, drinking can be perceived as neutralising the seeming control of the over-functionary by giving the drinker an edge over the relationship. The over-functioning spouse is unable to go anywhere she wants, annoy the spouse, or leave the spouse alone for fear of him drinking. The over-functions may contribute to the drinking by displaying anxious criticism or attempting to prohibit drinking through mother round initiatives of counter-control drinking behaviour by the under-functioning alcoholic spouse.

Flatcar was a smart 2001 film. Alcoholic families have lower problem-solving capacities than non-alcoholic families, both within the parents and within the family as a whole. Lack of cohesion and increasing conflict may emerge and worsen in alcoholic families as a result of poor communication and problem-solving skills. COAs are more prone than non-COAs to have disruptive behavioural problems and to be sensation seekers, aggressive, and impulsive.

Chalets me: lane. (2001) Living in a household with a non-recovering alcoholic can cause stress for all family members. It's possible that each individual will be affected in a unique way. This stress is not experienced or reacted to in the same manner by every alcoholic family. The non-alcoholic spouse's level of dysfunction or resiliency is a major determinant in how difficulties affect children.

P Kodandaram In 2002, the problem of alcoholism was found to affect not just the lives of alcoholics, but also the lives of people around them, resulting in social, occupational, and psychological harm. Due to drinking, marital strife is unavoidable. Grubisic – Hicm, Ljubin T, and Kozaric – Kovacic D were compared. The wives of alcoholics were less outgoing than their non-alcoholic counterparts. Neurotisms and psychoticism were not distinguished. Wives of alcoholics exhibited less extraverted behaviour before marriage, according to this self-evaluation of their behaviour. Psychiatric treatment was used more frequently on the wives of alcoholics during their marriage.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Alcoholism as an impact on marital functioning and relationship. Studies were conducted on three major areas that is the study of the alcoholic's spouse emphasizing personality traits, study of the alcoholic's spouse emphasizing personality traits, study of the alcoholic's children and the alcoholic's family interaction. Alcoholism creates many stresses in the life of wives. It affects psychologically and socially. It brings so many conflicts in their relationships. The present study was an attempt to study the psychosocial burdens marital disharmony and adjust-mental burdens of the wives of alcoholics.

Aim of the Study

To assess the life burden of wives of alcoholic. The researcher in the present study has tried to identify the levels of psychosocial and marital –harmony and adjust-mental problems faced by the wives of those who are addicted to alcohol

Objectives of the Study

- ❖ To understand the socio – demographic background of the wives of alcoholics.
- ❖ To understand psychosocial problems faced by the wives of alcoholic
- ❖ To understand the adjust-mental problems of the wives of alcoholics
- ❖ To understand the marital disharmony among the wives of alcoholics.
- ❖ To suggest measures, to overcome burden face by the wives of alcoholics.

Scope of the study

In India alcoholism is one of the leading causes of death and this alcoholism paves the way of family disorder, suicides, and other calamities. This alcoholism has a deep connection with person's behavior, thoughts, personality etc. Because of the above said factors, the researcher motivated to select this topic and to deal with alcoholic person's wives. This study helps to understand the level of problems both psycho-social, faced by the wives of alcoholics with respect to personal, family, divisional and socio-economic aspects.

Sample

Since it was not possible to fix the exact size of the Universe (Floating population) the researcher adopted purposive sampling of selecting the sample size. The researcher collected data from inpatient and outpatients till the sample size **eighty** are reached.

TOOLS OF DATA COLLECTION

The information was collected from the respondents with the interview schedule which has prepared by the researcher it is very helped to study the socio-economic and psychological problems of the wives of alcoholics. The researcher also had discussion with counselor in order to know more information about he wives of alcoholics and their problems.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS**Table 1: DISTRIBUTION BASED ON THE AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS**

S.No	Age	No.of Respondents N=80	Percentage
1	20-25	12	15
2	26-30	20	25
3	31-40	16	20
4	Above 40	32	40
Total		80	100

The above table shows that (40%) of respondents belonged to the age group of above 40 years, (25%) of respondents belonged to the age group of 26-30 years. Another (20%) of respondents belonged to the age group of 31-40, and (15%) percent of respondents belonged to the age group of 20-25 years.

Table 2: EDUCATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.No	Education	No.of Respondents	Percentage
1	Primary	8	10
2	Secondary	16	20
3	Higher Secondary	28	35
4	Graduate	16	20
5	Post Graduate	7	9
6	Others	5	6
Total		80	100

The above table indicates that the majority of the respondents (35%) were educated till Higher secondary, (20%) of respondents were educated till secondary and graduate respectively, (10%) the respondents educated till primary,(9%) of the respondent were educated till Post Graduate,(6%) of the respondents were studied another courses.

Table 3: DISTRIBUTION OF THE „OCCUPATION“ OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.No.	Occupation	No.of Respondents	Percentage
1	House wife	28	35
2	Agriculture	8	10
3	Coolie	20	25
4	Self employment	9	11
5	Government employee	5	6
6	Professional	10	13
Total		80	100

The above table shows (35%) of respondents were house wives, then (25%) of respondents were Coolies, (13%) of respondents were Professional workers,(11%) of respondent were self employed,(10%) of respondent were agricultural workers. Minority (6%) of respondents were Government employees.

Table 4: DISTRIBUTION OF THE „INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.No.	Income(monthly)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Up to 2000	13	16
2	2001-3500	17	21
3	3501-5000	31	39
4	5000 and above	19	24
Total		80	100

The above table indicates majority (39%) of respondents belonged to the income group of 3501-5000. (24%) of respondents belonged to above 5000 income group,(21%) of respondent belonged to 2001-3500 income group, minority (16%) of respondents had income up to 2000.

Table 5: DISTRIBUTION OF THE RELIGION OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.No	Religion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Hindu	35	44
2	Muslim	20	25
3	Christian	25	31
Total		80	100

The above table indicates majority (44%) of respondents belonged to Hindu religion, (31%) of respondents belonged to Christian religion and remaining (25%) of respondents belonged to Muslim religion.

Table 6: DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESIDENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.NO	Residence	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Rural	32	40
2	Urban	12	15
3	Semi-urban	20	25
4	Slum	16	20
Total		80	100

The above table indicated majority (40%) of respondents were lived in Rural area,(25%) of respondents were lived in Semi-urban,(20%) of respondents were lived in Slum, remaining (15 %) of respondents were lived in urban areas.

Table 7: DISTRIBUTION OF THE FAMILY OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.NO.	Family	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Nuclear	68	85
2	Joint	12	15
Total		80	100

The above table shows that the vast majority (85%) of the respondents belonged to Nuclear family and the remaining (15%) of the respondents were belonged to Joint family.

Table 8: DISTTRIBUTING OF RESPONDENT“S ACCEPTENCE TO THEIR HUSBUND“S DRINKING HABIT

S.No	Acceptance	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	5	6
2	No	75	94
Total		80	100

The above table shows that the vast majority (94%) of respondents had not accept the drinking habit of their husband and minority (6%) of respondents had accepted the drinking habit of their husband.

Table 9: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT'S SHOWING THEIR DEBT DUE TO HUSBAND HABIT.

S.No	Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	48	60
2	No	32	40
Total		80	100

The above table reveals that majority (60%) of respondents had debts, remaining (40%) of respondents had no debts due to their husband's alcoholic habit.

Table 10: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS FAMILY'S RELATIONSHIP TOWARDS THEIR RELATIVES

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Average	44	55
2	Good	15	19
3	Poor	21	26
Total		80	100

The above table shows that majority (55%) of respondent's husband had an average relationship (19%) of respondent's husbands had good relationship remaining (26%) of husbands had poor relationship.

Table 11: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT'S FEELING WORRY TOWARDS THEIR PROBLEMS

S.No	Worry on their problems	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	56	70
2	No	24	30
Total		80	100

The above table shows that majority (70%) of respondents were worried about their problems because of their husband's drinking habit remaining (30%) of respondents were not worried because of their husband's drinking habit.

Table 12: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS FEELINGS TOWARDS THEIR LIFE.

S. No	Feeling towards life	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	54	68
2	No	26	32
Total		80	100

The above table shows that majority (68%) of respondents felt that there is no meaning for their life. Remaining (32%) of respondents had no such kind of feeling.

Table 13: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT ON THE BASIS OF ISOLATION

S. No	Feeling of isolation	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	59	74
2	No	21	26
Total		80	100

The above table shows that the majority (74%) of respondents had feeling of isolation; the minority (26%) of respondents had not such kind of feeling.

TABLE 14: DISTRIBUTION RESPONDENT'S FEELING OF HELPLESSNESS

S. No	Feeling of helplessness	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	61	76
2	No	19	24
Total		80	100

The above table shows that the majority (76%) of respondents had feeling of helplessness the minority (24%) of respondents had not such kind of feeling.

Table 15: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT ON THE BASIS OF SUICIDAL IDEA

S. No	Feeling of suicidal idea	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	52	65
2	No	28	35
Total		80	100

The above table indicates that all most all (65%) of respondents had suicidal ideas, remaining (35%) of respondents had no suicidal ideas

Table 16: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT'S ACCORDING TO HUSBAND'S AFFECTION TOWARDS THEM

S. No	Husband's affection towards them	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	37	46
2	No	43	54
Total		80	100

The above table shows that the majority (54%) of respondents' husband had no adequate affection towards them remaining (46%) of alcoholic husband had affection to their wives.

Table 17: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS ON THE BASIS OF PHYSICAL HARRASSMENT

S. No	Particular	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	61	76
2	No	19	24
Total		80	100

This table shows that the majority of the alcoholic husbands (76%) made physical harassment on their wives and the remaining (24%) hadn't made any physical harassment on their wives.

Table 18: WISH FOR DIVORCE

S. No	Particular	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	14	17
2	No	66	83
Total		80	100

The above table shows that the majority (83%) of respondent's hadn't wished for a divorce from their husbands while (17%) wish for divorce.

5. FINDINGS, SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

This chapter contains the main findings of the data presented in the previous chapter. The main findings are about the life burden of wives of alcoholics. The major pictures of alcoholic's wives are very pathetic; she is a dingiest woman retaining her possession. The major problem is she has anxiety about the future of her children. The role of father and mother are combined here. The mother, she is struggling hard to keep the family in the traumatic situation she has faced due to this alcoholism which has physical, mental and emotional implication.

MAJOR FINDINGS

The data collected by the researcher was analyzed and interpretations were made. Based on the analysis of the data, the following findings are presented.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

- Among the total 80 respondents studied (40%) of the respondents were between the age group of 41 and above.
- Among the total 80 respondent's majority (70%) of them had more than secondary education.
- Among the total 80 respondent's (35%) of them are house wives.

- Among the 80 respondents (76%) of respondents had come under the income group below
- 5000
- Among the total 80 respondents studied (44%) were Hindus
- Among the total 80 respondent's (40%) of respondents were from rural areas
- Majority of the total 80 respondents studied (85%) of them belonged nuclear family
- Among the total 80 respondent's (69%) of them had arrange marriage.

PSYCHOSOCIAL PROBLEMS

- Among 80 respondents a vast majority (94%) were not accepted the drinking habit of their husbands.
- Among the 80 respondents (61%) of respondents felt jealous to that neighbors are leading happy life.
- Among the 80 respondents (76%) of respondents were despaired.
- Majority (54%) of respondents had lack of understanding among family members.
- Majority (64%) of respondents husbands create nuisance of relatives houses.
- Majority (55%) of respondents had an average relationship with their relatives.
- Among the 80 respondents studied a vast majority of 94% alcoholic wives expressed their fear about their children future due to the drinking habit of husbands.
- Among the 80 respondents studied 70% of the alcoholic wives worried about their problem a lot.
- Majority (68%) of respondents felt that, there is no meaning for their life.
- 76% of them were felt that their life is miserable due to the husband's habit.
- 74% of them felt isolation from the society.
- Among the 80 respondents 76% of alcoholic wives were felt that they are helpless.
- Vast majority (65%) of them had suicidal ideas.

MARITAL DISHARMONY

- ◆ Vast majority (79%) of respondents husbands were used to get angry with them irrationally.
- ◆ Among the 80 respondents majority (86%) of respondents were not find any happiness in their married life.
- ◆ Majority (54%) of respondent's husband had no adequate affection towards them.
- ◆ Among the 80 respondents (56%) had felt that their husbands suspect them.
- ◆ Among the 80 respondents majority (76%) of respondents had the physical harassment from their husbands.
- ◆ Among the 80 respondents (83%) of respondents had not wish for a divorce from their husbands.
- ◆ Among the total 80 respondents majority (59%) of them were not asked for divorce.
- ◆ Among the total 80 respondents majority (91%) of them were felt that drinking habit of the husbands were an obstacle of their future goals.

ADJUSTMENTAL PROBLEMS

- 56% of respondent's husbands had not co-operation in household chores
- Majority (64%) of respondents had concentration in household chores .
- Among the total 80 respondents all most all 54% of respondents had anger to children when their husbands come with drunk.
- Among the 80 respondents vast majority 64% had proper attention towards their children.

- Among the total 80 respondents had felt that 48% of their husbands had good relationship with their children.
- 88% of respondents were felt that they are over burdened with all responsibilities.
- Among the 80 respondents majority (80%) respondent's family had an adequate communication among the family members.

Suggestions

The study was conducted among the wives of alcoholics and studied there psychosocial burdens, marital disharmony and their adjust mental burdens. The findings of the study have suggested the following factors. When husband has turned to alcoholism the each and every wife has to perform dual role in the family it will naturally create some problem to wives. So develop facilities to help the wives to adjust the role change. Make alcoholics anonymous meeting more effective and gives the wives an opportunity to share their feelings with others it will reduce their tension to certain extend. Make facilities for giving financial support to the wives because in most of the cases husbands are irresponsible about the family matters and then wives have to deal with the financial matters in the family. Developing programs for family interaction of the alcoholics. The functioning of the existing agencies should be improved for giving more assistance to the total family of the alcoholics. To provide adequate awareness classes of both alcoholics and wives & children.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gillian – Social Pathology (center of social science 3 addition Alcoholism)
- [2] Lamer- Social Pathology – me Grew hill serious in sociology & anthropology.
- [3] Madan- jnelian social problem.
- [4] Ghan KH-social welfare volxxxv No:5 August 1988 FM ander stress.
- [5] Dr. Madan-social welfare vol xxx v No:5 August 1988 where women head the families.
- [6] Rose H.L. journal or family issues vol x No:1 march 1990 problematic families.
- [7] Jagloe EN –journal of family issue, vol x No:1 march. Adjustment to widowhood & divorce.
- [8] Shah KN – the Indian journal of social work July 1989.
- [9] Peter Samuel – would health action – vol- xxx 1989.
- [10] Cbaudary M- S. welfare . vol xxx 1988.
- [11] Cotton (NS) – The familiar incidence of alcoholism. A review journal of studies on alcohol (1979).
- [12] Windle, Michael, Concepts & Issues in COA research alcohol health & research world. Vol.No. 3: 185- 191. 197.
- [13] Mutluri, A. (2020). The Youth of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) and their Livelihood Practices in India. *Antrocom: Online Journal of Anthropology*, 16(2).
- [14] Mullahy & Sinelaler – maternal alcohol consumption during any time of pregnancy.
- [15] Kodan doram –P- Personality of wives of alcoholics Indian journal of clinical psychology .